

BOOK REVIEW:

ECO TOURISM AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Ecotourism in North East India:
With Reference to Arunachal Pradesh
by Maila Lama, Anshah Publishing House,
Patparaganj, Delhi (2014); pp 1-124, Rs 600.

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This book, with seven chapters, is an outcome of the author's PhD Thesis that discusses interesting issues on ecotourism. In the introductory chapter the author highlights the importance, concept, emergence and definitions of ecotourism that contributes to economic development and if properly managed it can be beneficial to public as well as private managers. This chapter includes objectives, hypothesis, methodology and brief discussion of the study area chosen for Ecotourism potential in Arunachal Pradesh. Although the state being rich in resource endowments it is one of the most backward states in India and focus on promotion of tourism can be one of the best ways of generating internal revenue, employment, income generation and development of the state. In this book the author has attempted to estimate the economic value of ecotourism in Tawang and West Kameng districts of Arunachal Pradesh. Objectives of the study include a) to study the socioeconomic characteristics of tourist b) to examine the variables influencing visitation rate and to estimate the value of ecotourism by estimating the consumer surplus c) to calculate the willingness to pay among the tourist for developing adventure tourism d) to assess the potential negative impacts of tourism on environment e) to identify the major challenges for promotion of ecotourism and suggest measures to overcome those challenges.

Chapter two gives the Review of Literature based on economic valuation on environmental goods that play an important role in conservation policies and such studies could be used to demonstrate conservation of nature and result in economic benefits to people. The author has also discussed on economic value of environmental goods in terms of 'use value' and 'non-use value' and techniques in measuring value such as Travel Cost Method, Revealed Preference Approach, Stated Preference Approach and Contingent Valuation Method. The author has concluded that in spite of the fact Northeast Region of India is endowed with rich natural resources only few studies have been undertaken to estimate recreational and ecotourism value of natural environment. Hence such study is important in conservation of environment.

Chapter three discusses on socio economic profile of the tourist in Arunachal Pradesh. The author has pointed that the state of origin of most tourists were from USA, UK, Italy and Germany and none from Asian Countries. The authors study on Age Group found that domestic tourist was of 45-60 years whereas foreign tourist was 60 years and above. Educational Level found none were reported to be illiterate. Occupation of both category tourists showed most were salaried employees. As per study on whether family oriented, group travel or travelling alone revealed only few domestic tourists travelled alone and most foreign tourist preferred to travel with own family and least were the single travellers. Information on tourist spots in state revealed majority of domestic tourist knew through print media followed by word of mouth, internet, travel agent, official sites and foreign tourist knew through internet and print media. The type of tour performed found most visited on self-arranged and rest on package tour. Frequency of visit found most were first time and few more than once. Regarding facilities both category tourists were not satisfied with road conditions and transport facilities but were still willing to visit the state again. Number of foreign tourist desired to avail home stays to know local people and their culture. Based on these facts the author has stressed that Arunachal Pradesh has good potential for Ecotourism and formulation of proper policies and guidelines to avert damages to natural environment is needed.

Chapter four focuses on Tourism Growth and Structure of Tourist Demand. Blessed with natural endowments Arunachal Pradesh attracts visitors from all around the world. Trends in tourist arrival showed, inflow till 2003 was low due to fluctuations in the state. However, the study showed domestic tourist constituted 98 % and foreign tourist accounted only 2%. Comparing Arunachal Pradesh with states of Northeast in tourist arrival the author has explained Assam accounted for major share in domestic tourist inflow followed by Meghalaya and

Sikkim. Arunachal Pradesh ranked fifth in total domestic tourist arrival showed very low but improving over the years. Growth rate of domestic tourist arrival in different Northeast states from 2006-2012 revealed yearly average growth of domestic tourist arrival in Arunachal Pradesh was highest followed by Sikkim and Meghalaya. Most domestic tourist was budget groups desiring to travel at cheaper cost by public means and majority of high income foreign tourist preferred better facilities and avail home stays which indicated a necessity to develop modest and luxury tourism facilities. Motivational aspects show domestic tourists came for enjoying natural beauty and recreation and foreign tourists for knowing people and culture. Tourist arrival was found highly seasonal. Accommodation facilities revealed majority stayed in hotels followed by lodge. Tourist willingness to participate in adventure tourism indicated that both local and foreign tourists were interested in selected tourist spots such as trekking, river rafting and paragliding and only few in cycling, rock climbing, bungee jumping, ropeways, ice skating etc. Tourist expenditure revealed most domestic tourist spent in accommodation followed by food, beverages and least on local transport. Similarly, tourists also spent on handicraft items. Analysis of expenditure composition showed tourist spent least of total expenditure on local transport and most tourist hired vehicles from Assam to visit areas as the state lacked railways and airport. Overall the author says there is a need for development of tourism in the study area for which the Government should undertake investment

Chapter five examines the estimation of the recreational and ecotourism value. The values from natural environment are classified into use value (fuel, wood, timber, minerals, water, non-timber products, and recreation) and non-use value (existence value, altruistic value, bequest value). Based on the analysis the author shows non-use value often exceeds use value where tourism with its high direct use value play a vital role as an incentive for protection of natural environment and the non-consumptive environmental goods are associated with benefits from recreational activities. This is where the concept of ecotourism comes in where natural resources are potential in ecotourism areas. However due to non-availability of market price, economic benefits of ecotourism areas are not accurately known. However, by applying statistical tools, the author has found that visitation rate is inversely related to total cost travel and positively related to annual household income and age. Even though level of education is an important factor which should positively impact visitation rate it was found to have positive but insignificant impact in the study. A brief on contingent valuation is also given where many studies used to estimate the value of ecotourism. It involves the use of survey questions asking people's preferences about their willingness to pay or willingness to accept compensation for improvement. Finally, the author's analysis revealed that the recreational value of ecotourism on tourist spot selected in study area was found very high and indicated strong potentiality for ecotourism development for which the state planner's role is important in boosting tourism.

Chapter six provides environmental impacts of tourism development. The authors review of literature on tourism impact shows negative impact on environment. Arunachal Pradesh is in its initial stage of tourism development hence identification of potential negative impact of tourism on its environment was felt necessary. The Delphi technique was considered suitable for the study that Delphi Technique of Green in their assessment of environment impact was stemming from tourism project in England. The Delphi results found solid waste accumulation had high negative impact followed by traffic congestion, depletion of wildlife, destruction of forest, sewage problems, degradation of landscape, public health problems, drainage problems, deterioration of water quality, and depletion of aquatic life. The author has indicated for conservation of natural environment, education of environment to tourist and other stakeholders is a must and economic benefits of tourism to local folk serves as an incentive as local support in conserving the natural environment.

The seventh chapter gives an overall conclusion of this study and throws light on important policy implication giving suggestions for sustainable development of tourism in Arunachal Pradesh.

On the whole studies associated with evaluation of ecotourism projects are very useful for everyone who is interested in ecotourism studies. Despite growing number of Eco tourist, research in this field has been limited in other north eastern states that have a good potential for ecotourism. Hence in filling this gap there is a need for more research contributions in future in other areas and states that could contribute in poverty alleviation and development of the rural poor. The book is more useful to environmentalists, researchers, students on tourism and policy makers to understand more on tourism related issues.